

Training Evaluation Form

District..... School code Teacher code

Please indicate your impressions of the items listed below.

Training components	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1. The training gave me general understanding of the critical thinking about health.	<input type="radio"/>				
2. The training gave me a clear overview and flow of all lessons.	<input type="radio"/>				
3. I can navigate through the resources, and I know where I can find all that I need on the website	<input type="radio"/>				
4. Now I understand all teaching strategies relevant for teaching critical thinking about health	<input type="radio"/>				
5. The training gave me teaching tips that I need to consider while teaching CHOICE lessons	<input type="radio"/>				
6. I am confident that I understand and can teach all 10 lessons	<input type="radio"/>				
Competences					
7. The training met my expectations.	<input type="radio"/>				
8. I will be able to apply the knowledge learned.	<input type="radio"/>				
9. The training objectives for each topic were identified and followed.	<input type="radio"/>				
Training materials					
10. The content was organized and easy to follow.	<input type="radio"/>				
11. The materials distributed were pertinent and useful.	<input type="radio"/>				

Trainers

- 12. The trainer was knowledgeable.
- 13. The quality of instruction was good.
- 14. The trainer met the training objectives.
- 15. Class participation and interaction were encouraged.
- 16. Adequate time was provided for questions and discussion.

17. How do you rate the training overall?

- Excellent Good Average Poor Very poor
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18. What aspects of the training could be improved?

19. What was most useful?

20. What was least useful?

21. Other comments?

THANK YOU FOR YOUR PARTICIPATION!